

The word *adu* “cook” and the logogram “man with bread” / “baker” of Linear A tablets

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Abstract

In the first part of the Linear A tablet HT 88, different professional groups are listed. In the second part, six people are listed by names. The most interesting part of the tablet is the word *adu* followed by the logogram “man with sign *ka*”, which evidently clarifies the meaning of the word *adu*. The logogram “man with sign *ka*” denotes “baker” because the sign *ka* is a schematic depiction of bread and because the word *ka* correlates well with the Hattic word *kait* “grain” (earlier it was shown that the language of Linear A is a dialect of Hattic). In the word *adu* the prefix *a-* correlates with the Hattic prefix *a-* functioning like a definite article, and the root *du* correlates with the Hattic root *tu* “to eat” / “eating” / “food”. Thus, the word *adu* can be translated as “these cooks” / “those cooks”.

Keywords: Linear A; Haghia Triada 88; Minoan Crete; Minoan language

1. Introduction

Linear A tablet Haghia Triada No. 88 (HT 88) is attributed to Late Minoan IB period (about 1500 – 1450 BCE). Sizes of the tablet are the following: 7 * 5.8 * 0.9 cm. The tablet has an inscription made by Linear A signs on one of its parts (Fig. 2). The tablet has no losses or chips, the text is completely preserved.

Fig. 1. Location of Haghia Triada in the island of Crete (image source – Akulov 2024b: 3)

Fig.2. Linear A tablet HT 88 (image source – Linear A 2026b)

Fig.3. Text of the inscription of HT 88 with numbered signs

In the first part of the inscription (signs 1 – 13) (Fig. 3) different groups of people are listed: *adu* (1, 2) logogram “man with syllable sign *ka*” (3) number 20, *reza* (5, 6), number 6 (7), *ni* (8), word separator (9), *kikina* (10 – 12), number 7 (13).

The logogram “man with sign *ka*” evidently denotes a certain professional group, so it is logical to suppose that in this part of the inscription different professional groups are listed.

In the second part of the inscription (14 – 42), people by names are listed: *Kiro* (14, 15), word separator (15), *Kupapa* (17 – 19), number 1 (20), *Kayu* (21 – 22), number 1 (23), *Kupanu* (24 – 26), number 1 (27), *Payare* (28 – 30), number 1 (31), *Samaro* (32 – 34), number 1 (35), *Datara* (36 – 38), number 1 (39), *kuro* (40 – 41), number 6 (42).

The word *kuro* means “total”, literally it means “there is” / “there are” or “[we] have” (Akulov 2023). The word *kuro* and the number 6 after it summarizes only names listed in the second part of the inscription.

The inscription of the tablet contains a list of people, not a list of food supplies distributed to different people (for more details see 2).

In this paper I want to clarify the meaning of word *adu* (signs 1, 2, Fig. 3), and the logogram “man with sign *ka*” (sign 3, Fig. 3).

2. Why the inscription of HT 88 is not about distribution of food supplies

Jh. Younger suggested that the inscription is about distributions of some amount of figs among 26 people who are denoted by the logogram “man with sign *ka*”. Younger suggests that sign 8 (see Fig. 3) is a logogram meaning “figs” (see Linear A 2026b).

However, this interpretation is incorrect.

First, after the logogram “man with sign *ka*” comes number 20, not 26 (see Fig. 3, sign 4). Number 26 can only be received if we add the number 20 that comes after the logogram “man with sign *ka*” to the number 6 that comes after the word *reza* (see Fig. 3, sign 7). However, it is important to note that in the text of the inscription these numbers have not been summarized, and it is obvious that they denote different groups of people. If it were 26 people, it would have been clearly stated in the text itself. Minoan household and business records are always simple in meaning, free of metaphors and riddles. The text of the inscription says about 20 people denoted by the logogram “man with sign *ka*” and about 6 people denoted by the word *reza*. And there is no evidence that these groups are the same, they are different.

Also, the structure of the inscription of HT 88 differs seriously from the structure of inscriptions which really describe distribution of food supplies.

If we take a look at, for instance, the inscription of the tablet HT 102 which really describes distribution food supplies among different groups of people we can see that the inscription has clear structure: first goes a word or a logogram denoting a certain group, then goes a logogram denoting a food supply, then goes numeric signs describing the amount of delivered food (Fig. 4).

Also, we can see that in this inscription, which talks about the distribution of food, the numerical signs come after the logograms denoting food and after the words denoting groups of people there are no numerical signs.

Also, we can see that numeric signs describing amounts of delivered food stand immediately after corresponding logograms, after logograms denoting wheat/grain and other food there are no additional words clarifying the meaning of logograms. The logograms themselves quite exhaustively describe what exactly needs to be provided. We see this on tablet HT 102, and it can also be seen on other tablets that say about food allocation.

Fig. 4. The structure of HT 102 (source of the original image – Linear A 2026d) (for more details about HT 102 see Akulov 2024b: 2 – 7)

The inscription of HT 88 is not about distribution of food at all. Sign 8 (see Fig. 3) in this context is not a logogram meaning “figs”, but is just plain syllable sign *ni*.

The inscription of HT 88 is a list of people.

The first part lists various professional groups (perhaps this is a request for sending different specialist), the second part lists six people by name.

3. The word *adu* and the logogram “man with sign ka”

3.1. The logogram “man with sign ka”

The word *adu* (signs 1 – 2, Fig. 3) and the logogram “man with sign ka” evidently are connected. The logogram is not separated from the word *adu* by a word separator, that is, the logogram is written to clarify the meaning of the word *adu*.

At first glance, this logogram depicts a man with a shield, but this assumption is incorrect. The sign which human figure of the logogram holds is Linear A sign *ka* .

The syllable sign *qe* as a symbol of shield can be seen as a part of logogram designating armorer (Fig. 6). This logogram can be seen, for instance, in the inscription of the tablet HT 89 (Fig. 5), the logogram “armorer” is a schematic representation of the main products manufactured by armorers.

Fig. 5. Logogram “armorer” in the inscription of HT 89 (image source – Linear A 2026c) (for more details about this inscription see Akulov 2024b: 16 – 21)

The syllabic sign *ka* *ka* actually is a schematic depiction of bread. In ancient times, bread of this shape was baked throughout the Mediterranean from the Bronze Age till the time of Roman Empire (see Fig. 6, 7).

Also, it is important to note that before it has been shown many times that the Minoan language is a dialect of Hattic, and that the Hattic language can be used directly to understand Minoan texts (Akulov 2017b, 2021a, 2021b, 2023, 2024a, 2024b, Desherieva 2025).

Making analysis of the Linear A inscription of HT 102, A. Akulov pointed out that in the text of HT 102 there is the word-form *i-ka* meaning “that grain”: in this word-form can be signled out the prefix *i-* that correlates well with the Hattic prefix *i-* that expresses the function of definite article, and the rest part of the word-form *ika* is its root – *ka* that correlates with the Hattic word *kait* “grain” (Akulov 2024b: 6).

And it is noteworthy that this word *ika* is written with the use of the sign *ka* .

The syllabic signs of Linear A definitely was created according to acrophobic principle: to write each syllable were used symbolic images of objects or beings whose names began with that syllable.

Fig. 6. Linear A signs *ka* and *qe*, and samples of ancient Egyptian bread (image source – Rubel 2021)

Fig. 7. Petrified panis quadratus from Pompeii (image source – Arta Alba 2023)

The syllable *qe* that is expressed by the sign that is used to depict shield correlates with Hattic word *kip* “to protect” (Akulov 2017a: 24 – 25).

And the syllable *ka* is expressed by the sign *ka* which is a schematic depiction of bread.

Thus, now it is possible to state that the logogram “man with sign *ka*” means “man with bread” or simply “baker”.

3.2. The word *adu*

As far as the word *adu* stands near the logogram “baker”, so it seems that the word *adu* also denotes a certain profession connected with food.

A very important inscription for understanding the meaning of the word *adu* is HT 85a where the word *adu* appears in a series of professional groups: *adu*, shipbuilders (a logogram denoting a shipbuilder is a schematic image of the frame of a ship), plain warriors (or workers), denoted by the logogram “man”, etc. (Fig 8).

Fig. 8. The word *adu* among other words denoting professional groups in HT 85a inscription (image source – Linear A 2026a)

Therefore, *adu* is not a personal name or a toponym, but the name of another professional group.

The initial *a* in *adu* evidently is a prefix functioning like a definite article.

The same prefix can be seen, for instance, in the form *asara* “those carpenters” from HT 89 (see Akulov 2024b: 17).

In the Hattic language there is the same prefix *a-* which is attaches to nouns and functions as a definite article or a demonstrative (Soysal 2004: 205).

And the remaining part – *du* evidently is the root.

This root can be compared to the following Hattic roots:

du / *tul* / *tur* – “to hit”, “to beat”, “to strike” (Soysal 2004: 317),

tuh / *duh* “to take”, “to hold” (Soysal 2004: 316),

tu “to eat” (Soysal 2004: 316).

Taking into account the fact that next to the word *adu* is the logogram “baker” I suppose that *du* should be correlated with Hattic *tu* “to eat”, “eating”, “food”¹, but not with other roots. I suppose that the form *adu* denotes people engaged in preparing food / cooks, but not those who possibly serve food.

Hattic /t/ can become /d/ in Minoan if it occurs in intervocalic position (Akulov 2024a: 20).

Also, It should be taken into account that there may have been some shift in meaning: the form that in Hattic meant primarily “to eat” in Minoan could have the meaning “to cook”, but in any case both meanings are related to food.

Thus, it is possible to say that in this context the word *adu* can be translated as “these cooks” / “those cooks”.

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¹ In Hattic there was fairly well-developed conversion: a root simply expresses a certain concept, but depending on the attached affixes, it could become either a verb or a noun. And therefore the root *tu* expresses not just meaning “to eat”, but meaning “food” in general.

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